

ELEGANT PERFUME SMELLED PEN

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ABSTRACT

It is known that nowadays the demand for cheap, high-quality and healthy ballpoint pens is growing day by day, which plays an important role in the growth of human thinking and worldview. Currently, despite the diversity of entrepreneurs engaged in the sale of canned goods, the company plans to sell its ballpoint pens at low prices and improve human health.

The pen plays a big role in our daily lives, but we don't always feel it. Here is some information about it:

1. The first pen was priced at \$ 12. Now you can buy a pen-radio with this money.
2. Ball pens were first introduced in 1945. Specialists received a patent for the production of ballpoint pens 57 years ago. More than 10,000 ballpoint pens were sold on the first day.
3. According to psychologists, those who bite the pen in the process of thinking are naturally prone to creativity.
4. 92% of the world's population uses the pen effectively.
5. Russia has a population of about 140 million, but uses 600 million pens a year.
6. For some reason, the leader of the Cambodian Indian tribe forbade the tribesmen to use a pen and carry it in their pockets. Anyone caught with a pen was shot dead.
7. A good pen can write about 50,000 words.

8. Angelica Unverhau, a woman from Germany, collects pens. Today, there are 160,000 types of pens in his collection.
9. 125 pens are sold every second around the world.
10. Every year, 100 people around the world die from pen stuck.

The invention of the ballpoint pen is officially the end of the 19th century, and the Hungarian journalist Laszlo Biro invented a pen similar to the modern ballpoint pen in 1938. He had to write a lot with a simple pen, and because the ink was required and left an ink stain when used, he began to create a "worry-free" pen. The invention seemed lucrative.

Almost immediately, the British Air Force purchased a patent for a ballpoint pen for its pilots. It was very inconvenient for them to use a pen during the flight. However, he soon re-registered his patent in Argentina and sold it to "Eversharp" company for \$ 1 million at a huge profit. The Argentine company launched the world's first ballpoint pens. Domestic sales were very

good: the cheapness and efficiency of the new device attracted a large number of buyers.

However, "Eversharp"'s decision to take over the world market was met with great frustration due to flaws in the patent system. The pen was only patented by the author in Hungary and Argentina. To prevent plagiarism, he had to obtain a patent for his invention in all countries of the world. Because it was an impossible task, the idea for ballpoint pens was stolen from Biro and Eversharp.

On June 10, 1943, Milton Reynolds, an American commuter, patented such a pen in the United States and began mass production. The pens began to be sold in very large quantities. 10,000 pieces were sold in a New York store in just one day. The author of the invention tried to defend his patent in an American court, but lost.

In 1958, the Frenchman Marcel Bick updated the ballpoint pen a bit and created the cheapest BIS template in production. BIS Corporation now controls one-third of the ballpoint pen trade market in the United States.

This day goes down in history as the date for the patenting of the first prototype of a small ballpoint pen - a ballpoint pen. The owner of this discovery is officially John Luad (USA). Although he presented his invention in October 1888, roughly modern-looking pens only became widespread in the late 1930s.

Hungarian journalist Josef Laso Biro has received a patent for a pen that we all know with our hands and eyes now. Biro, who is always obsessed with the obligation to carry ink with him and the stains left on the pen, is seriously concerned about creating a handy work tool. As a result of research, the ballpoint pen was born. The right to produce

it on a large scale will be acquired by the British Air Force. But for the second time he managed to monetize his invention on another continent - Latin America; Argentina's Eversharp company pays the lucky journalist \$ 1 million, which was unparalleled wealth at the time.

The new product quickly attracts attention with its cheapness and convenience. The compact textbook fell into the hands of Milton Reynolds, an American merchant traveling in Argentina. Reynolds, a master of his craft, estimates the benefits of this innovation. Upon inquiry, it was discovered that the invention was registered only in two countries, and, most importantly, has not yet entered the world's largest market - the United States, and no official documents have been signed in this regard.

In 1943, the merchant obtained a patent in the United States for someone else's invention, and began mass production. Reynolds was right: the ballpoint pen gained fame at lightning speed, selling 10,000 copies a day at the only Jimbel store in New York. True, the author of the discovery, Biro, wants to restore his rights through the courts, but his attempts do not yield the expected results.

This is not the end of the pen's task of "giving birth to millions." In 1958, Marcel Bick of France further simplified the pen mechanism and began production under the name BIS, at a lower cost. Thus was founded BIS Corporation, which today occupies a large share of the global training tool market, and its owner remains one of the richest people in the world.

The ballpoint pen was only patented in Hungary and Argentina. To be patented all over the world, the Biro had to travel all over the world and patent the pen in all countries. But he failed to do so, and as a result the idea of a ballpoint pen was stolen

from Biro and Eversharp. Milton Reynolds, an American traveling in Argentina, bought several ballpoint pens. Thinking of the benefits of this simple thing, Reynolds patented the ballpoint pen in the United States in 1943 and began mass production. 10,000 pens were sold in 1 store in New York City. Buyers were intrigued by the new pen's ability to write underwater. The idea stolen by Milton Reynolds turned him into a millionaire. The author of the idea failed to defend his patent in an American court.

It is a pen that calms the human nervous system, in which liquids from various fruits and flowers, in addition to ink, are placed in the pen using a separate small container. For example, liquids from roses, violets, kalas, chrysanthemums, carnations, etc. from flowers such as lemons, oranges, mandarins, apples, etc. are injected into the ink using a syringe.

The advantage of this pen is that several diseases related to the nervous system can be treated through the delicate scent emitted from it. For example, the stuttering of the tongue, the rupture of small nerve vessels in the body caused by intense nervousness, helps to counteract the effects of a stroke.

It also prevents several such dangerous cardiovascular diseases such as myocardial infarction, tachycardia, angina, heart attack. This method of treatment is widely used in China and India and is the cheapest method of treatment. Its name in medicine is called "aroma therapy". This can save a considerable amount of money spent on the treatment of the above diseases.

The main criterion in the development of the economy of our country, the full supply of the consumer market with goods and services, and economic relations between different owners should be activity based on

strict competition, fair competition and fairness.

At present, enterprises, organizations and entrepreneurs are faced not only with the problem of increasing the total volume of products and services, overful fillment of the plan, but also with the production, sale and provision of consumer goods and services. Regardless of the form of ownership, any entrepreneur must have its own position and share in the consumer market, to operate in a way that ensures high economic efficiency and profitability. At a time when the market economy is becoming a real practice, the strengthening and further development of any economy depends, first of all, on the rational structure of the economic business plan.

Business is a multifaceted term that reflects economic entrepreneurial activity aimed at achieving certain results. This activity is carried out on the basis of a certain procedure, and this set of procedures is called a business plan. Every modern entrepreneur, whether he is a member of the team or a private entrepreneur, has a business plan as the main program for the successful completion of his work. In a market economy, the assessment of entrepreneurial activity and the market, aimed at increasing the demand for each product or service, is the key issue and content of the business plan.

This project aims to produce ballpoint pens in the country in order to further meet the needs of the population of Syrdarya region, Gulistan and neighboring regions.

Conclusion:

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov had such views. "I know two honorable professions in the world, one is teaching and the other is medicine." Indeed, as a result of the opportunities provided by the President to

medical and medical personnel, I would consider the fact that the average life expectancy of our population is 73 years for men and 75 years for women as a result of the opportunities provided to the medical sector. Of course, our work in this area would be more developed if the proposed project is implemented in practice. In the future, in addition to selling the product, it is planned to distribute it free of charge to low-income families in need of social protection. In addition, people with disabilities who are disabled in generosity,

kindness, and hearing are also distributed to their homes as a gratuitous non-discriminatory aid.

Note: The income from the export is stored in the bank as a deposit for the implementation of future activities of the enterprise, ie for the future import of ink production technology, and the income and interest accrued by the bank to the depositor are used to achieve the above purpose.

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